
Atmospheric turbulence characterization under inhomogeneous inflow conditions using nacelle-lidar measurements

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Project abstract:

This PhD project is part of the Lidar Knowledge Europe (LIKE) project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 and led by DTU. The aim of the LIKE project is to promote training and education of young researchers in the field of laser-based remote wind measurement technologies, as well as increasing the utilization of these technologies in the industry. Wind lidars mounted on the nacelle of wind turbines, hereafter nacelle lidars, can be deployed in two modes: forward looking to scan the wind turbine in flow and backward looking to scan the wake of the wind turbine. Forward-looking nacelle lidars, in particular, have a great potential for improving the energy capture of wind turbines as they can potentially measure more effectively over the volume of air that interacts with the turbine when compared to traditional point-like nacelle anemometry, such as cup and sonic anemometers. Therefore, turbine control strategies, and load assessment and validation methods, among others, can enormously benefit from the applied use of nacelle-lidar measurements. Wind turbines typically yaw with the wind; thus nacelle lidars have the advantage, over traditional anemometry mounted on meteorological masts, of measuring radial velocities (and the variances of those) that are close or equal to the longitudinal wind speed component (and its variance), which is the main driver for load estimation, and a key parameter for power performance assessments and wake-deficit characterization. This PhD project aims at utilizing measurements from nacelle lidars to characterize atmospheric turbulence under inhomogeneous inflow conditions. In the last couple of years, methods have been devised to characterize turbulence with measurements from forward-looking nacelle lidars but those assume that the inflow turbulence is homogeneous. Such an assumption is only valid for very small and isolated wind turbines deployed on at and homogeneous sites. Modern turbines are now operating in the first 250 m of the atmosphere, where turbulence can largely vary with height, and "real" deployment sites can be different from at and homogeneous, which has an impact on the vertical (and horizontal) characteristics of turbulence. Further, wind turbines now rarely operate isolated but in wind farms and so the inflow is seldom homogeneous but wake-affected; wakes are characterized by being highly inhomogeneous and turbulent. This PhD study includes three main aspects: 1. An investigation on how to characterize the inflow with nacelle-lidar measurements under inhomogeneous conditions, e.g. flow under wake situations and flow interacting with very large wind turbines. 2. An analysis of the best ways and strategies to scan inhomogeneous inflow with nacelle lidars for optimizing the turbine's energy capture and for mitigation of the loads for both individual turbines and wind farms. 3. An evaluation of the benefits of retrieval of high-order wind field characteristics from nacelle-lidar measurements for both wake modelling and control strategies.

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Data Collection

Describe the data that will be collected.

1. Turbulence boxes:

Turbulence boxes are binary files containing float type data obtained from numerical simulation. The data in files that are ended with .u, .v and .w representing the wind speed fluctuations in longitudinal, lateral and vertical directions, respectively. The 100 turbulence boxes that are used in this PhD project are generated by Jakob Mann with simulation tool "[Mann 64bit turbulence generator](#)". In each turbulence box, the number of points in the three directions are $(N1;N2;N3) = (8192;64;64)$. The 100 turbulent boxes are generated with 100 different seeds. The turbulence boxes together with the corresponding input files are available in DTU disk ri-veadbs03. One turbulence box in three dimensions require 384MB disk space.

The turbulence boxes are durable, independent and can be loaded in different simulation environment. The storage disk is open to DTU employees. They are reproducible with Mann 64bit turbulence generator and same input parameters. The turbulence boxes are used as virtual turbulence wind fields to simulate nacelle-lidar measurements.

2. Nacelle-lidar simulation in Python (code):

Measurement of different lidar systems are simulated numerically in Python using 100 pre-calculated turbulence boxes, which are mentioned above. The simulated lidar systems are DTU SpinnerLidar, Leosphere 4-beam Lidar, Avent 5-beam lidar, ZX 50-beam lidar, lidars with 6 beams and 51 beams. The conic angle and focus distance can be adjusted to see the impact of the scanning geometry on the accuracy. The simulated lidar measurements are used to retrieve the mean wind speed and the Reynolds stress. The results are saved as .pickle files. The code are uploaded and versioned on [GitHub](#). Specific nomenclatures of lidar are used to ensure the code is understandable.

3. SpinnerLidar measurement from field campaign:

Measurement data from SpinnerLidar is needed to investigate the methodology of deriving wind profile as well as the spatial distribution of velocity variances over the rotor disk under inhomogeneous inflow conditions. The data of Doppler-shifted spectrum from SpinnerLidar is preferable. One of the candidates for the needed data set is the [SpinnerLidar measurements for the CCA V52](#). With the same equipment, the data set from [LICOREIM](#) project is also considered. However, for studying the inhomogeneous turbulence, the shortcoming of these measurement is that the wind turbine is small and the inflow over rotor disk is not inhomogeneous enough. Another candidate is the [SpinnerLidar measurements from TotalControl project](#) on a big Samsung wind turbine. However, the data availability is not very high because some beams in the bottom were blocked by the big turbine blades. Also, the met-mast is far away from the wind turbine. There will be some difficulty to validate the analysis result. The data and documentation from field campaigns are stored on a file server managed by DTU.

4. Machine learning algorithm (code):

Supervised machine learning models will be implemented in Python. The models can be used for classification and regression. One of the objectives of these models is to estimate the wind speed and Reynolds stress at different locations over the rotor disk. Another use of the machine learning models is to estimate the Mann parameters from SpinnerLidar measurements. The SpinnerLidar measurements will be used to train, validate and test the model. The code and relevant documents will be uploaded and versioned on [GitHub](#).

5. HAWC2 simulation for DTU 10 MW research wind turbine:

Simulation .htc files and the input data of aerodynamics, hydrodynamics, elasticity and servo parts of the DTU 10MW wind turbine will be needed. They are ASCII files and can be obtained from [HAWC2](#) software. The wind data and controller data will be modified in this project. The HAWC2 simulation files will be used to simulate the load and power production with different wind models and controllers. The simulation results will be saved as .dat and .sel file together with the input files in my local drive. Metadata (probably a technical report) will be produced to summarize the simulation setup and results.

6. FLORIS:

[FLORIS](#) is a controls-oriented engineering wake model implemented in Python by NREL. I got the access of the code from GitHub [NREL/floris](#) page. FLORIS is considered to be used to simulate the loads and power estimation by accounting for the spatial heterogeneity in wake modelling inside the wind farm.

7. Simulink model and DLL of controller:

Simulink model of individual pitch controller will be implemented in Matlab. To evaluate the benefit of using high-order wind field moments for control application, the PI controller for individual pitch control will be re-tuned considering spatial heterogeneity of turbulence wind field. The Simulink model of the controller will be later compiled to DLL, which can be loaded into different aero-elastic simulation tools, such as HAWC2 and Bladed.

Describe any restrictions to the data.

The HAWC2 simulation tool is owned by DTU. FLORIS is licensed under the [Apache License](#), Version 2.0 (the "License").

Data Storage

Describe the IT infrastructure to be used.

All data, computer codes, notes and articles used in the PhD project are saved in DTU [Onedrive](#) and are continuously backed up to the server. In addition, all data and computer scripts are also planned to be uploaded to the [DTU Wind Energy Gitlab Source Code Server](#) (run by DTU), [GitHub](#) and [DTU Data](#).

Documentation

Describe the metadata to be associated with the data.

For the machine learning algorithm, metadata will be produced to describe the detail of the used model as well as the data set used as the input to the model. For HAWC2 simulation, technical reports will be produced to explain the simulation setup and summarize the results.

Describe the types of documentation that will accompany the data.

The computer codes created in the PhD project will be thoroughly commented and/or documented to ensure that they will be understandable and easy to use. The computer codes that are uploaded and versioned on [GitHub](#) will be accompanied by "README.md" file that will explain the content and use of code in greater detail. Besides, the data sets generated in this PhD project will be accompanied with documents describing the format of the data, when and how the data sets were computed and the post-processing of the data sets. In addition, valuable findings and results will be shown and published as journal papers or technical reports.

Data Sharing

Describe which data will be shared.

All methods and results developed in this PhD project are planned to be disseminated through journal articles, reports, presentations and posters. The data, computer codes and documentations are planned to be shared on [GitHub](#), [DTU Data](#) and [Zenodo](#) with open access to the extent possible.

Describe how the data will be shared for possible reuse.

Journal articles, reports, presentations and posters are planned to be shared on [Zenodo](#) and [DTU Orbit](#). Data, computer codes and documentation will be uploaded to [GitHub](#) and the [DTU Wind Energy Gitlab Source Code Server](#). The GitHub uploads will also be linked to Zenodo to make sure that all information is easy to find. Zenodo, DTU Orbit and GitHub are linked to my personal [ORCID](#).

Long-term Preservation

Describe how data will be archived beyond the scope of the research project.

Before archiving the data, all data, computer codes and documentation will be examined to ensure that only relevant, re-runnable, well documented materials are saved. The long-term preservation will be made on my personal M-drive and a personal external hard-disk. In addition, data and computer codes will be saved on the [DTU Wind Energy Gitlab Source Code Server](#), [DTU data](#) and [GitHub](#). Articles, reports, presentations and posters will be saved on Zenodo and [DTU Orbit](#).